

GRID AND MARKET HUB PLATFORM TO ENABLE A DATA-DRIVEN SMART GRID ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the grid and market hub (gm-hub) platform that is being developed as part of the Horizon 2020 InteGrid project and its capabilities to enable data-driven services on the top of an existing smart-grid infrastructure. The gm-hub will bring together the interests of the electricity sector's stakeholders, which will make their decisions with better information, based on data provided by the DSO such as electricity consumption data and technical validation of flexibility. Moreover, it also supports the exchange of flexibility potential from the lower grid nodes, enabling predictive management of technical constraints, and enables third-parties services such as a local social network for contextual feedback about energy consumption in order to foster behavioural demand response in a local community.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Distribution System Operator (DSO), as a regulated company, is primarily responsible for ensuring continuity of supply, efficiency and power quality. The deployment of smart grids infrastructures motivated a discussion about the current and future roles of the DSO, namely acting as neutral market facilitators in undertaking core functions. Regarding the neutral market facilitator principle, the EDSO opinion is that DSOs already performs this role by “facilitating economic activity through channelling electricity to consumers and giving transparent and non-discriminatory connection, access and switching”. A more sophisticated service that the DSOs can provide is the provision of smart meter data, in non-discriminatory manner and with the consumer’s consent, to the retailers (market players) for billing purposes, as well as to other stakeholders like energy services companies (ESCo).

The InteGrid project is aimed at providing a cloud-based grid and market hub (gm-hub) solution to support the provision of services in a neutral and standardized way between customer relationship manager/neutral market facilitator (primary roles of this central platform) and stakeholders like electricity retailers, transmission system operator (TSO), aggregators, group of consumers and energy services providers (e.g., Energy Services Company - ESCo, data analytics companies). The main objective is to facilitate market access allowing new business models

and services while ensuring efficient and secure network operation as well as the highest standards of data security.

This paper describes the overall architecture for the gm-hub along with the services it provides. The cornerstone of this market facilitator lies within the discretionary management of consumer’s consents, allowing customer data to be shipped from the DSO domain in the context of services. These services could either be deployed directly into the gm-hub or forwarded to third-party systems through custom REST APIs.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: section 2 provides the concept for the neutral market facilitator role; section 3 and section 4 respectively approach the basic and advanced services offered, together with their associated business models; section 5 covers the data management plan considered and section 6 approaches the security concept of the gm-hub; finally section 7 covers related concepts and work and section 8 wraps-up the paper.

2. GRID AND MARKET HUB CONCEPT

The gm-hub consists in a centralized cloud-based platform with decentralized data storage that provides the integration link between the stakeholders of the project (e.g., service providers, service users) to build an integrated environment, enabling demand response, smart grid functions and storage.

Figure 1- gm-hub data storage architecture.

The gm-hub operates in a regulated domain, thus all the embedded services are regulated and subjected to a suitable regulatory framework for data management and exchange. Furthermore, this central platform should be perceived as an enabler of third-parties’ services that can emerge in the gm-hub ecosystem [1]. The gm-hub ecosystem comprises multiple external roles from market

players connected to the distribution system, TSO, market operator, consumer and services providers. These stakeholders will benefit from Business to Business (B2B) and Business to Customer (B2C) services available in the gm-hub. A third-party can extract business value from the services offered by the gm-hub and offer a range of B2B and B2C services external to the gm-hub central platform

Moreover, the gm-hub also establishes a direct cooperation between DSO and TSO, with the market operator as intermediary for the ancillary services market, in terms of flexibility pre-qualification, activation and management. Finally, it also enables the use of local flexibility for technical constraints management, particularly at the low voltage (LV) grid level.

3. GM-HUB BASIC SERVICES

The gm-hub provides a set of basic services from where different stakeholders obtain a distinct set of functionalities based on their role, as depicted in Figure 1, namely:

Consumer: can perform two main actions: **request meter data** and **authorize data sharing**. The first use case corresponds to download its own data in a readable format (in CSV). The second one corresponds to authorize third parties to use their data (in XML).

Figure 2 - Allowed roles in the gm-hub.

Market player: apart from the **registration**, this group of users can request consumption data or provide information of flexibility. In order to perform the former, the user should **request an authorization**, which the customer needs to allow. In addition, the market player can **sign the legal agreements**, required to access the customer data.

Data Science Company: this actor has the well-defined role of performing analytics. This group of users **makes use of the already described use cases** that are related to data access.

4. GM-HUB ADVANCED SERVICES AND BUSINESS MODELS

The gm-hub provides a set of advanced services. These services are data-oriented and allow the transmission of consumer and grid data to other stakeholders within the gm-hub. Each one of these services creates a distinct domain, where clients provide their strict consent. Each one of the services, along with the associated business model is afterwards discussed.

Traffic light concept (gm-hub B2B): this service has two main objectives: (a) conduct a predictive (which contrasts with a “traditional” reactive traffic light approach) technical validation of flexibility for frequency control, activated by the TSO, from distributed energy resources connected to the distribution grid; (b) monitoring of flexibility activation/repression by detecting areas with frequent limitation in terms of flexibility use (input signal for the DSO planning department).

Flexibility exchange to support grid operation (gm-hub B2B): this service powers the exchange of information about the available flexibility in the distribution grid, per grid user, communicating the pre-booked (pre-activation) of the available flexibility, in order to solve technical constraints in the MV and LV grid.

Information feedback about contracted power (gm-hub B2C): this service provides information to the consumer regarding the usage of contracted power, considering operating grid conditions, season of the year and the Home Energy Management System (HEMS) flexibility from intelligent load management functions.

Alarms about high consumption patterns (gm-hub B2C): this service generates alarms to LV consumers about high consumption patterns related to excessive electrical energy consumption. The limits and thresholds are defined according to parameters and preferences defined by the gm-hub customer.

Gather consumption profile (third-party B2B service): in this service, an ESCo or a retailer uses the gm-hub’s infrastructure to advertise services to a consumer. The service itself aims to predict the consumption profile of a client in order to offer added value services that will increase engagement between consumer and retailer.

Residential Energy Resources Sizing (third-party B2C service): in this service an ESCo or a retailer offers a service to a LV consumer aiming for an optimal sizing of residential energy resources. This will include the sizing of storage, PV and water heater.

5. DATA MANAGEMENT

European regulations now impose strict control on the

usage of consumers' data. This takes shape in light of the General Data Protection Regulation [2] and the data protection Directive 95/46/CE [3]. Therefore, data sharing to and from the neutral market facilitator is bound by the following primitives (among others):

- a. the unambiguous consent given by the consumer;
- b. the identification of the required data, the purpose for the processing, along with all its constraints (e.g., the retention period).

In the rest of this section we cover the data flows from the gm-hub to the consumer and to third-parties.

From gm-hub to consumer

These services involve the transfer of energy consumption data from the gm-hub to the low-voltage customer. However, the gm-hub, being merely a data hub, does not store data. Instead, it sends a request to the DSO, the DSO applies validation, estimation and editing (VEE) functions and returns the requested data to the gm-hub. The data or the information computed on it is then made available for the user to download it. The services where this strategy is applied are:

- a. **Download my data:** The user is able to request its data to be downloaded from the DSO in a human readable format;
- b. **Feedback about contracted power:** The user is able to customize consumption patterns, receiving recommendation regarding the contracted power;
- c. **Alarms about high consumption patterns:** The user configures and receives alarms that were forwarded from the gm-hub, when the consumption patterns do not conform to what has been configured.

From gm-hub to third-parties

These services depend on information exchanged between the gm-hub and market players and will be analysed in this section. As a result of some being B2B services, the final user can either be a low-voltage consumer or a medium-voltage consumer. The third-party (e.g., ESCOs, data analytics company, etc), will in turn be responsible for the data entrusted to them. In order to provide its services at the gm-hub, all third parties must register at the platform and provide their personal information (tax paying number, address, etc.). They also must define the service (or services) they will provide in terms of scope and objective. All this information is to be stored at the gm-hub and will be used to generate the Terms & Conditions for each service, that will be presented to the user whenever a new service is subscribed. The services where this strategy is applied are:

- a. **Residential energy resources sizing:** Allows a retailer to run optimisation algorithms and calculate operational proposals, benefits and sizing;
- b. **Consumption profile for service enhancement:** Allows a third party to receive data from costumers and suggest them services according to their consumption profiles.

6. SECURITY CONCEPT

The risk-based Secure Software Development Lifecycle is recommended for all developments. As an essential part of the project, a risk assessment was conducted through threat modelling of all software component, producing a security risk assessment report. Threat modelling is a systematic approach to uncover security threats of a particular product, solution or use case at design time and to support reaching a secure design. It is one of the methods used within the secure software development lifecycle of leading market software companies.

The goal is to identify security threats early in the development cycle so that they can be included in a security plan and control procedures can be planned.

Risk Assessment matrix

Risks distribution is depicted in Figure 3. Green identifiers correspond to demo risks and red identifiers correspond to the real system's risks.

Figure 3 - Risk assessment matrix.

Identified Risks and Mitigation

The main identified risks are covered in this section. For each one we provide a description and mitigation action.

Secure Authentication (A1): The gm-hub is a central service hub for a large variety of connection parties. It's crucial for the system's availability and integrity to identify all the communication partners, so no masquerading at gm-hub scenarios could take place. The gm-hub applies SSL connections with client authentication using X.509 certificates. Moreover, all inbound and outbound communications are encrypted (based on X.509

certificates) and two-factor authentication is used.

Man-in-the-middle attacks (A2): Due to a possible flaw in the authentication of encryption process within one of the connections, an attacker could try to use that and impersonate himself as legal communication partner. To mitigate this issue, the gm-hub applies modern SSL cryptography algorithms and will regularly update these algorithms, patching any security breaches that in the meantime could be discovered.

Authentication policies (A3): Passwords are not secure by the concept because they could be disclosed, stolen or guessed. To mitigate this issue, strong password policy is considered, which is complemented by the used of identity X.509 certificates.

Secure permission model (B1): The TSO, market operator, consumer and services providers, data science companies and third parties can extract business value from the services offered by the gm-hub (different scenarios). Unauthorized access to other party's scenario might endanger overall system integrity. To mitigate this, a secure permission model was setup, ensuring that no other party can benefit from permissions granted to other registered stakeholders.

Built-in backdoors (B2): Backdoors, unintentionally left by developers are quite often present in large development projects. Malicious code ("backdoor") might be found and used by an attacker to run OS commands on the production system. To mitigate this issue, frequent security check is conducted, analyzing the code and providing reports to the development team.

Cross-site scripting (C1): This type of vulnerability is very wide spread, esp. for web applications, because it is hard to prevent such vulnerabilities. Attacking bots (spiders) analyze web applications automatically. To mitigate this issue, all input and output values passed to and from the gm-hub are sanitized, preventing sensitive information leaks.

SQL injection (C2): This type of vulnerability is very wide spread, esp. for web applications, because it's hard to prevent such vulnerabilities. Attacking bots (spiders) analyze web applications automatically. To mitigate this, all SQL statements considered are sanitized, preventing malicious coding of being passed into the database systems supporting the gm-hub.

Directory path traversal (C3): The gm-hub shall be using file processing for logging procedures. "Directory Path Traversal" vulnerability is very wide spread, especially for web applications, because it is hard to prevent such vulnerabilities. Attacking bots (spiders) analyze web applications automatically and may automatically promote SQL injection or cross-site

scripting malicious procedures. To mitigate this "whitelisting" mechanisms are considered to safeguard files and prevent misuse of files (e.g., unauthorized configuration files).

Buffer overflow and memory corruption (C4): Malicious communication partners (dialog or background user) may ship maliciously crafted inputs to gm-hub (input especially crafted to exploit "buffer overflow" anomaly). To mitigate this, all web-based technologies considered will be frequently updated, installing all security patches required to fix any security breaches found.

XML based attacks (C5): At least one XML standard shall be used for integration of the gm-hub with the external systems: CIM IEC 61968. Malicious communication partner (dialog or background user) sends maliciously crafted XML to gm-hub (input especially crafted to exploit XML based attacks). To mitigate this, XML documents will not be trusted for data sharing between partners, protecting the gm-hub from malicious attacks from external partners.

Denial of service (C7): Currently, ordering DoS attack against a company is cheap and easy, thus presenting significant threat in the modern world. To mitigate this issue, Anti-DoS proxy is set up, which not only filters incoming traffic by source IP, but also validates it on the application level. Additionally, a recovery plan, which covers procedures needed to quickly restore the system in case of unavailability of some of the components of the server is in place.

Cross-site-request-forgery (C8): This type of vulnerability is very wide spread, esp. for web applications, because it is hard to prevent such vulnerabilities. Attacking bots (spiders) analyze web applications automatically. XSRF attacks endanger business data and processes. To mitigate this issue, the gm-hub considers the use of URL rewriting method (insert user's session ID in the URL) so an attacker could not guess the victim's session ID.

Clickjacking (C9): This type of vulnerability is very wide spread, especially for web applications, because it is hard to prevent such vulnerabilities. To mitigate this issue, the gm-hub makes sure that X-Frame-Options is set up to "SAMEORIGIN" value (Apache Tomcat web server configuration), which means that a top document could be only displayed over the same domain from where is originated.

Insecure URL redirection (C10): This type of vulnerability is very wide spread, esp. for web applications, because it is hard to prevent such vulnerabilities. Attacking bots (spiders) analyze web applications automatically. To mitigate this issue, URLs from untrusted sources are verified and filtered.

7. RELATED CONCEPTS AND WORK

In order to unlock the full potential of demand response programs, achieving a long-term household engagement is essential. To incentivize this engagement, one mechanism that is used is the benefit of monetary savings. However, in practice, the monetary savings are too small to promote a behavioural change compared to the comfort of not making any effort and the initial interest in pure energy feedback (i.e. from in-home monitoring or energy apps) diminishes over time [4]. Based on this, a need for a new type of engagement mechanism became apparent. The premise for any service that is used with regularity is that it creates a real and concrete benefit for the end-user. So, what if energy feedback is not given in within an energy app, but instead as part of a more natural context that gives the end-users a clear benefit? After evaluating the needs of households, reversing the increasing trend of “globally connected yet locally isolated” [5] was selected as a suitable context. The proposed solution is a local social network called LocalLife, a sustainability-oriented social network for people that live close to each other, aimed at facilitating and enriching local life by helping neighbours connect. It is based on secure neighbour-to-neighbour interactions, that are geographically bound to the buildings and the neighbourhood. This is the context in which collective energy feedback and load shifting goals are provided. The concept is based on recent work [6] that suggest that social influence combined with a sense of community responsibility could promote intrinsic motivation and increase engagement. As such, it is a low-cost, and highly scalable engagement mechanism that only relies on a forecasting signal and access to smart meter data.

For the current pilot testing in Stockholm, Sweden, a solution with one of the local DSO is used [7] However, this approach is not scalable in Europe, as separate agreements and integrations would be needed for almost every DSO. The existence of a centralized European gm-hub with an easy and standardized way to access the household consumption regardless of where the household is located, would enable scalability and replicability of third-party smart grid services like LocalLife across Europe, thus potentially increasing the household engagement and grid flexibility.

8. CONCLUSION

This paper described the overall concept for the gm-hub, the central platform and services to support demo sites, use cases and to align with the architecture of the demo sites, including interfaces and messaging. The main objective of this platform is to facilitate market access allowing new business models and services while ensuring efficient and secure network operation as well as highest standards of data security. The gm-hub operates in a regulated domain, and it is an enabler of third-parties' services (B2B and B2C) that can emerge in the gm-hub ecosystem.

The InteGrid project shows that the increasing awareness of prosumers about data protection and business value of their smart meter data demands for a revision of the current data management paradigms and business use cases. In the framework of this project, the gm-hub and its services will be installed and demonstrated in Portugal and Slovenia and the value of the proposed approaches will be assessed in a real-world scenario.

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